

Sparse Adaptive Mesh Refinement

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Abstract

Mesh adaptation plays a central role in efficient numerical simulation of partial differential equations, particularly in regimes where resolving localized features is critical. Classical adjoint-based and optimization-driven refinement strategies, while accurate and principled, are often computationally expensive and difficult to scale in large or repeated simulation settings. This motivates solver-independent and computationally efficient alternatives for identifying refinement regions.

In this work, we study two complementary paradigms for solver-independent mesh adaptation. The first is a sparse recovery-based formulation of **discretization entity marking**, where mesh refinement is posed as an inverse problem to recover a sparse entity-wise refinement indicator using operator-driven sensing and structured sparsity, resulting in an explicit and interpretable selection of mesh entities for refinement. To improve scalability, we incorporate operator-weighted scaling and sketching strategies while preserving reconstruction quality.

The second is a machine learning-based formulation using graph neural networks trained with a physics-informed classification objective. The model takes flux gradient features defined on a mesh graph as input and is supervised using the Euler residual as a refinement signal. This approach learns refinement indicators directly from data without explicit operator structure, enabling fast inference at the cost of reduced interpretability and dependence on training data.

All experiments are conducted on steady two-dimensional Euler equations with a fixed mesh density setup. Performance is evaluated across variations in sketching strategy and associated parameters. The sparse recovery approach shows stable convergence, robustness to perturbations in the right-hand side, and resilience under aggressive sketching. The learning-based models achieve competitive refinement performance and capture dominant flow features, though finer-scale structures are less consistently resolved compared to the sparse formulation.

Overall, the results highlight a fundamental trade-off in solver-independent mesh adaptation: structured sparse recovery provides interpretability through explicit refinement indicators and controlled optimization behavior, whereas graph-based learning offers flexibility and fast evaluation. These approaches represent two ends of a spectrum, and the appropriate choice depends on whether robustness and interpretability or computational efficiency and data-driven adaptability are prioritized.

Contents

1	Introduction and Motivation	1
2	Governing Equations	1
3	Discrete Problem Setting	2
4	Mesh Adaptation Strategies	2
4.1	Gradient-Based Adaptation	3
4.1.1	Stacked Cell-Centered Gradient (CellGrad)	3
4.1.2	Stacked Vertex-Based Gradient (VertexGrad)	3
4.2	Jump-Based Adaptation	3
4.2.1	Cell-to-Face Jump Operator (Jump)	3
4.3	Unified Operator Notation	4
5	Sparse Mesh Adaptation via Perturbed Operator Approach	4
5.1	Sparse Recovery Interpretation	5
5.2	Interpretation as a Refinement Indicator	5
6	Adjoint-Based Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR)	5
7	Classical Sparse Methods	6
7.1	ℓ_0 Methods	6
7.1.1	Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)	6
7.1.2	Iterative Thresholding Methods (IHT / HTP)	7
7.2	ℓ_1 Methods	7
7.2.1	FISTA	7
8	Randomized Dimensionality Reduction for Sparse Recovery	7
8.1	Problem Setup	7
8.2	Sketching Approach	8
8.3	Sketching Matrices	8
8.4	Accuracy–Efficiency Trade-off	8
9	Weighted Operators and Singular Value Analysis	8
9.1	Structural Properties of the Unweighted Operator	9
9.2	Singular Value Structure of the Unweighted Operator	9
9.3	Weighted Operator for Feature Sensitivity	9
9.4	Effect on Singular Value Spectrum	10
9.5	Implications for Sketching	10
9.6	Spectral Role of Operator Weighting	10
10	Physics-Informed Classification via Residuals	10
10.1	Node Features and Graph Construction	11
10.2	Physics-Informed Scoring and Refinement Selection	11

11 Preliminary Study: Graph-Based Refinement Baselines	12
11.1 Graph Convolutional Network (GCN)	12
11.2 Graph Attention Network (GAT)	12
11.3 Model Complexity and Training Results	13
11.4 Interpretation	13
12 Training Setup	13
12.1 Mesh Generation and Dataset Selection	13
12.2 Hyperparameter Tuning	13
13 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Annealed Mass Constraint	14
13.1 Setup	14
13.2 Loss Function Recall	15
13.3 Annealing Schedule	15
13.4 OMP-Informed Prior Assumption	15
13.5 Interpretation	15
13.6 Coarse-to-Fine Learning Phases	16
13.7 Empirical Reliability and Limitation	16
13.8 Optimization	16
14 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-Model High-Precision Ensemble Approach	17
14.1 Motivation and Main Idea	17
14.2 Setup	18
14.3 Top- q Selection by Each Sub-Model	18
14.4 High-Precision Assumption for Small Prediction Budgets	19
14.5 Why Small q Improves Precision	19
14.6 Ensemble Prediction by Set Union	19
14.7 Bounded-Coverage Property	20
14.8 Duplication and Nonlinear Growth of Coverage	20
14.9 Coverage Interpretation	20
14.10 Statistical Viewpoint	21
14.11 Asymptotic Coverage of the Discontinuity Region	22
14.12 Interpretation of the Asymptotic Guarantee	23
14.13 Relation Between the Ensemble Size and the 30% Region	23
14.14 Tunable Design Parameters	23
14.15 Interpretations	24
15 Error Analysis	24
15.1 Area-Weighted Error Norms	24
15.2 Reference Solution	25
15.3 Conservative Interpolation	25
15.4 Nearest-Neighbor Interpretation	25
15.5 Convergence Criterion	26
16 Geometry and Problem Setup	26

17	Boundary Conditions	26
17.1	Inlet	27
17.2	Walls	27
17.3	Outlet	27
17.4	Remarks	27
18	Mesh Generation and Refinement	28
19	Mesh Refinement Results	28
19.1	Sparse Recovery Results	28
19.1.1	No Sketching or Scaling	28
19.1.2	Sketching without Scaling	31
19.1.3	Sketching with Scaling	34
19.1.4	Singular Value Spectrum Analysis	36
19.1.5	Influence of Sketching Dimension	38
19.1.6	Effect of Perturbation Scaling Factor	39
19.2	Machine Learning Results	39
19.2.1	Preliminary Study: Graph-Based Refinement Baselines	39
19.2.2	Physics-informed Classification Loss with Fine-tuned Hyperparameters	40
19.2.3	Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-Model High-Precision Ensemble Approach	41
20	Error Analysis Results	43
20.1	Classical Methods	43
20.1.1	ℓ_0 Method: OMP	43
20.1.2	ℓ_1 Method: FISTA	46
20.2	Combined Iteration-wise Error Comparison for Different Methods	48
20.3	Sketching Study: Influence of Sketching Dimension on OMP	48
20.3.1	OMP: Without Scaling	49
20.3.2	OMP: With Scaling	49
20.4	Perturbation Study: Effect of Right-Hand Side Scaling	49
20.4.1	ℓ_0 Method: OMP	50
20.4.2	ℓ_1 Method: FISTA	50
20.5	Machine Learning Assisted Refinement	50
20.5.1	Baseline Physics-informed Classification Loss	51
20.5.2	Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-model High-precision Ensemble Approach	52
21	Discussion	52
22	Conclusion	53

1 Introduction and Motivation

A fundamental challenge in the numerical solution of partial differential equations (PDEs) is the accurate resolution of localized features such as shocks, boundary layers, and steep gradients without prohibitive computational cost. Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) addresses this by selectively increasing resolution in critical regions. A central component of AMR is **discretization entity marking**, which identifies mesh entities (cells or nodes) that should be refined.

In practice, discretization entity marking is often based on heuristic indicators such as gradient magnitude or residual norms, as well as adjoint-based error estimation. While adjoint-based methods are mathematically rigorous, they are computationally expensive and difficult to scale in large nonlinear simulations, since an adjoint system must typically be solved for each output functional or timestep.

In this work, we formulate AMR entity marking as a **sparse recovery problem**, where the goal is to recover a sparse refinement indicator over mesh entities. Since sharp solution features are spatially localized, only a small fraction of mesh entities requires refinement. This motivates sparse optimization and compressed sensing techniques for identifying refinement regions in a principled and efficient manner.

In parallel, we investigate a graph neural network (GNN)-based approach as an alternative methodology for AMR entity marking. While the sparse formulation is grounded in optimization and compressed sensing, the GNN approach learns refinement patterns directly from mesh and solution features. These two approaches are developed and analyzed independently.

The two methods provide complementary strategies for identifying refinement regions, enabling computational resources to be focused where they are most needed and improving overall efficiency without sacrificing accuracy.

2 Governing Equations

All numerical experiments are based on the two-dimensional steady compressible Euler equations, obtained from the Navier–Stokes system by neglecting viscous effects [1].

The governing equations in conservation form are:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial y} = 0, \tag{1}$$

where the conserved variables are

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho v \\ \rho E \end{bmatrix}, \tag{2}$$

and the inviscid fluxes are given by

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ (\rho E + p)u \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ (\rho E + p)v \end{bmatrix}. \tag{3}$$

Here, ρ denotes density, (u, v) the velocity components, E the total energy per unit mass, and p the pressure given by the ideal gas equation of state.

All simulations are performed using **SU2** [2]. The resulting solutions exhibit sharp discontinuities (e.g., shocks), which serve as targets for the mesh adaptation strategies developed in this work.

Figure 1: Representative solutions exhibiting discontinuities for different values of θ_2 .

3 Discrete Problem Setting

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be discretized by an unstructured mesh of N control volumes. A cell-centered finite-volume discretization of the compressible Euler equations yields a discrete solution (here representing the scalar density field)

$$\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4)$$

The resulting nonlinear algebraic system can be written in operator form as

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{u} = \mathcal{B}, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{u})$ denotes a state-dependent discrete operator induced by numerical fluxes, and \mathcal{B} accounts for boundary contributions.

In practical CFD solvers such as **SU2** and OpenFOAM [3], this operator is not assembled explicitly. Instead, its action

$$\mathbf{v} \mapsto \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{u}) \mathbf{v} \quad (6)$$

is evaluated implicitly via flux-based computations, yielding a matrix-free formulation that avoids storing the full operator and accommodates its nonlinear dependence on the state.

As a result, the discrete operator is not directly accessible for downstream tasks such as error estimation and mesh adaptation. This motivates the development of solver-independent approaches that rely only on the computed solution \mathbf{u} and mesh connectivity, without requiring explicit operator construction.

4 Mesh Adaptation Strategies

This work investigates two principal, non-machine-learning strategies for mesh adaptation, aimed at identifying cells or nodes that require refinement. All operators are defined on the cell-centered density field $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Vertex-based quantities are used only as auxiliary reconstructions where required.

4.1 Gradient-Based Adaptation

The first strategy is based on the observation that large solution gradients indicate regions requiring refinement. Since only cell-centered values are available, gradients are reconstructed using discrete operators derived from mesh connectivity.

4.1.1 Stacked Cell-Centered Gradient (CellGrad)

A least-squares reconstruction over local cell neighborhoods defines a stacked gradient operator

$$\begin{bmatrix} \partial_x \mathcal{U} \\ \partial_y \mathcal{U} \end{bmatrix} = D_{\text{cell}} \mathcal{U}, \quad D_{\text{cell}} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{\text{cell}}^x \\ D_{\text{cell}}^y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N \times N}. \quad (7)$$

The operator D_{cell} is sparse and constructed using local least-squares reconstructions over neighboring cells.

Figure 2: Stacked cell-centered least-squares gradient reconstruction.

4.1.2 Stacked Vertex-Based Gradient (VertexGrad)

For triangular meshes, gradients can alternatively be reconstructed using vertex-based interpolation. Vertex values are first obtained by averaging neighboring cell values, followed by a local linear reconstruction over each element. This yields

$$\begin{bmatrix} \partial_x \mathcal{U} \\ \partial_y \mathcal{U} \end{bmatrix} = D_{\text{vertex}} \mathcal{U}, \quad D_{\text{vertex}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N \times N}, \quad (8)$$

where each row has strictly local support.

Figure 3: Vertex-based gradient reconstruction.

4.2 Jump-Based Adaptation

4.2.1 Cell-to-Face Jump Operator (Jump)

Discontinuities are captured using a face-based jump operator

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathcal{J}\mathcal{U}, \quad (9)$$

where $J \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{faces}} \times N}$ is a sparse matrix with at most two nonzeros per row. For an interior face f shared by cells (c_L, c_R) ,

$$b_f = \mathcal{U}_{c_L} - \mathcal{U}_{c_R}, \quad (10)$$

with boundary faces set to zero.

Figure 4: Face-based jump operator capturing discontinuities.

4.3 Unified Operator Notation

All mesh adaptation indicators can be expressed in the unified linear form

$$\mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{D} \in \{D_{\text{cell}}, D_{\text{vertex}}, J\}$.

Gradient-based operators capture smooth but steep variations, while the jump operator captures discontinuities. All operators are sparse and locally supported.

Notation: CellGrad, VertexGrad, and Jump refer to the corresponding operator families used throughout this work.

5 Sparse Mesh Adaptation via Perturbed Operator Approach

We reinterpret the operator relation

$$\mathbf{D}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}) \quad (12)$$

as a feature measurement system, where \mathbf{D} is a fixed linear operator (e.g., CellGrad, VertexGrad, or Jump), and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u})$ represents the corresponding extracted feature field.

Let \mathbf{u}_0 be the computed solution. We introduce a perturbed feature field in the measurement space,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{B}} = (1 - \epsilon)\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0), \quad 0 < \epsilon < 1, \quad (13)$$

and define a response state \mathbf{u}_1 such that

$$\mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}_1 = \tilde{\mathbf{B}}. \quad (14)$$

Subtracting the two systems yields

$$\mathbf{D}\Delta\mathbf{u} = \epsilon\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0), \quad \Delta\mathbf{u} := \mathbf{u}_0 - \mathbf{u}_1. \quad (15)$$

This relation characterizes how the operator \mathbf{D} propagates perturbations in the feature (measurement) space.

5.1 Sparse Recovery Interpretation

The feature field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0)$ is typically concentrated near shocks and steep gradients. Therefore, the inverse problem

$$\mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} = \epsilon \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0) \quad (16)$$

admits solutions that may be either spatially diffuse or highly localized.

We seek the sparsest representation consistent with the measurements:

$$\min \|\Delta \mathbf{u}\|_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} - \epsilon \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0)\|_2 \leq \epsilon. \quad (17)$$

Sparse recovery algorithms (e.g., OMP, IHT, HTP, FISTA) promote solutions with minimal support, thereby concentrating $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ in regions where the feature field is most localized.

5.2 Interpretation as a Refinement Indicator

The magnitude of $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ serves as a refinement indicator:

- **Smooth regions:** Responses are distributed, resulting in small values of $|\Delta u_i|$.
- **Discontinuities:** Responses concentrate on a small subset of degrees of freedom, producing large values of $|\Delta u_i|$.

Thus, the support of $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ identifies regions requiring mesh refinement.

6 Adjoint-Based Adaptive Mesh Refinement (AMR)

Adjoint-based mesh adaptation is a classical approach in which refinement is guided by the sensitivity of a target functional with respect to local discretization errors [4]. This typically involves solving an additional adjoint problem associated with the governing equations, followed by the construction of error indicators that combine primal and adjoint information.

While this framework provides goal-oriented refinement and strong theoretical grounding, it requires access to the discrete operator and the solution of an additional adjoint system, which can be computationally expensive and challenging to scale in large or repeated simulations.

In contrast, the proposed approach avoids adjoint computations entirely and instead identifies refinement regions through operator-based perturbation and sparse recovery, relying only on the computed solution and mesh connectivity.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of adjoint-based adaptive mesh refinement.

7 Classical Sparse Methods

We consider sparse recovery techniques for solving linearized perturbation systems of the form

$$\mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} = \Delta \mathbf{B}, \quad (18)$$

where \mathbf{D} is a discrete feature operator (e.g., CellGrad, VertexGrad, or Jump), $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ is the unknown correction field, and $\Delta \mathbf{B}$ represents a localized perturbation in the feature space.

In the present setting, $\Delta \mathbf{B}$ is typically concentrated near shocks or sharp gradients, while the operator \mathbf{D} distributes this information across the domain. This leads to an inverse problem that admits both diffuse and localized solutions. We seek sparse solutions in $\Delta \mathbf{u}$, which act as refinement indicators identifying regions where features are concentrated.

Classical approaches can be broadly categorized into ℓ_0 -based and ℓ_1 -based methods.

Figure 6: Sparse recovery–based mesh adaptation: localized feature perturbations lead to sparse reconstruction of refinement indicators.

7.1 ℓ_0 Methods

ℓ_0 methods aim to directly minimize the support of $\Delta \mathbf{u}$, producing exactly sparse solutions. These approaches iteratively identify the most significant components contributing to $\Delta \mathbf{B}$.

7.1.1 Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)

OMP is a greedy algorithm that incrementally builds a sparse solution by selecting columns of \mathbf{D} that are maximally correlated with the residual [5]. At iteration k ,

$$j_{k+1} = \arg \max_j \left| (\mathbf{D}^\top \mathbf{r}_k)_j \right|, \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_k = \Delta \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k$.

The solution is updated via a least-squares solve restricted to the selected support. Here, each column of \mathbf{D} corresponds to a mesh entity, so OMP effectively identifies a subset of cells driving the feature perturbation, leading to localized refinement near discontinuities.

A sparsity level $s = \lfloor \alpha N \rfloor$ is prescribed, with $\alpha = 0.3$ in our experiments.

7.1.2 Iterative Thresholding Methods (IHT / HTP)

Iterative Hard Thresholding (IHT) and Hard Thresholding Pursuit (HTP) compute sparse solutions through gradient-based updates combined with support selection [6]. A typical IHT update is

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+1} = H_s \left(\Delta \mathbf{u}_k + \gamma \mathbf{D}^\top (\Delta \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u}_k) \right), \quad (20)$$

where $H_s(\cdot)$ retains the s largest-magnitude entries.

HTP improves this by performing a least-squares projection on the selected support at each iteration, improving stability and reconstruction accuracy.

7.2 ℓ_1 Methods

ℓ_1 methods promote sparsity via convex relaxation, replacing the combinatorial ℓ_0 problem with a tractable optimization problem.

7.2.1 FISTA

FISTA solves the ℓ_1 -regularized least-squares problem

$$\min_{\Delta \mathbf{u}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} - \Delta \mathbf{B}\|_2^2 + \lambda_{\ell_1} \|\Delta \mathbf{u}\|_1, \quad (21)$$

using accelerated proximal gradient iterations.

The method combines gradient descent with soft-thresholding and Nesterov acceleration, leading to improved convergence over standard iterative shrinkage methods.

In contrast to ℓ_0 approaches, FISTA produces approximately sparse solutions, often resulting in smoother but less sharply localized refinement regions.

Remark The choice between ℓ_0 and ℓ_1 methods reflects a trade-off between exact support recovery and computational tractability. In practice, ℓ_0 methods yield sharper localization of refinement indicators, while ℓ_1 methods produce more diffuse but stable reconstructions.

8 Randomized Dimensionality Reduction for Sparse Recovery

The sparse recovery formulation introduced in the perturbed operator framework leads to large-scale linear inverse problems in feature space. Although the operator \mathbf{D} is sparse, the overall system dimensionality scales with the number of mesh entities, making sparse recovery algorithms computationally demanding for large meshes.

To address this, we employ techniques from randomized linear algebra, commonly referred to as **sketching**, to construct reduced systems that preserve the essential operator structure while significantly lowering computational cost.

8.1 Problem Setup

From the perturbed operator formulation, we obtain the linear system

$$\mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} = \Delta \mathbf{B}, \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is a fixed discrete feature operator (e.g., CellGrad, VertexGrad, or Jump), $\Delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the unknown sparse response vector, and

$$\Delta \mathbf{B} = \epsilon \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_0) \tag{23}$$

is the prescribed perturbation of the extracted feature field.

In this setting, the system represents an overdetermined linear inverse problem in feature space. The objective is to recover a sparse $\Delta \mathbf{u}$ that explains the perturbation under the action of \mathbf{D} .

For large meshes, both m and n are large (often of comparable magnitude), making iterative sparse recovery methods computationally expensive despite the sparsity of \mathbf{D} .

8.2 Sketching Approach

To reduce computational cost, we introduce a sketching matrix

$$S \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times m}, \quad s \ll m, \tag{24}$$

and pre-multiply the system to obtain the reduced problem:

$$S \mathbf{D} \Delta \mathbf{u} = S \Delta \mathbf{B}. \tag{25}$$

We define the **sketching factor** as

$$\text{SF} = \left\lfloor \frac{m}{s} \right\rfloor, \tag{26}$$

which quantifies the degree of dimensionality reduction.

The resulting system contains fewer constraints while approximately preserving the operator-induced structure of the original problem. This reduced system can be directly used within sparse recovery algorithms such as OMP, IHT, HTP, or FISTA.

8.3 Sketching Matrices

We employ two standard randomized constructions for the sketching matrix. In the Gaussian sketch, entries are independently drawn as $S_{ij} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1/s)$, providing strong concentration properties. In the Rademacher sketch, entries take values in $\{+1, -1\}$ with equal probability, enabling efficient matrix-free implementation and making it suitable for large-scale problems.

8.4 Accuracy–Efficiency Trade-off

Sketching reduces the number of constraints while approximately preserving the mapping between the perturbation $\Delta \mathbf{B}$ and the response $\Delta \mathbf{u}$. This is particularly effective since the solution admits a sparse representation in the canonical basis, and only a small subset of degrees of freedom dominates the reconstruction. The sketch size s (or equivalently the sketching factor SF) controls the trade-off between computational efficiency and accuracy of the reduced system.

9 Weighted Operators and Singular Value Analysis

In the sparse adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) framework, the properties of the underlying linear system play a central role in determining the effectiveness of sparse recovery and randomized

sketching techniques. Using the unified operator notation introduced in Section 4.3, the system can be written as

$$\mathbf{D}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{B}, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{D} denotes a discrete operator (cell-to-cell gradient, vertex-to-cell gradient, or jump operator), and \mathbf{B} is the corresponding extracted feature field. The operator \mathbf{D} is constructed solely from mesh connectivity and therefore does not incorporate solution-dependent information.

9.1 Structural Properties of the Unweighted Operator

All operators considered in this work share a common structure: they are sparse, locally supported stencil operators defined on a uniform triangular connectivity graph. Each row of \mathbf{D} corresponds to a local stencil involving neighboring cells or vertices, and the pattern of connectivity is spatially uniform across the mesh.

As a result, the operator does not preferentially emphasize any region of the domain. Each stencil contributes in a similar manner, and no solution-dependent scaling is present in the construction of \mathbf{D} .

This structural uniformity implies that the mapping induced by \mathbf{D} does not exhibit strong directional bias, which is reflected in its spectral properties.

9.2 Singular Value Structure of the Unweighted Operator

Due to the uniform stencil construction and connectivity-driven nature of \mathbf{D} , its singular value spectrum exhibits weak decay and tight clustering. There is no clear separation between dominant and negligible modes.

From a linear-algebraic perspective, this indicates that the operator behaves like a uniformly scaled mapping, where all directions in the solution space contribute in a comparable manner. As a result, the operator does not exhibit an intrinsic low-dimensional structure that can be easily exploited by randomized dimensionality reduction techniques.

This lack of spectral decay has an important consequence: sketching provides limited compression benefit in this regime, since no small subset of directions dominates the action of the operator.

9.3 Weighted Operator for Feature Sensitivity

To introduce solution-dependent structure into the operator, we define a weighted formulation:

$$\mathbf{D}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{D}, \quad \mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{B}), \quad (28)$$

with corresponding weighted feature representation

$$\mathbf{B}_w = \mathbf{B}^2. \quad (29)$$

This weighting amplifies rows associated with large feature magnitudes (e.g., strong gradients or jumps), while suppressing contributions from smooth regions. Consequently, the operator becomes sensitive to localized structures in the solution.

9.4 Effect on Singular Value Spectrum

The introduction of weighting modifies the spectral properties of the operator. In contrast to the unweighted case, the weighted operator $\mathbf{D}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{D}$ exhibits a more pronounced decay in its singular value spectrum.

This behavior reflects the emergence of dominant directions associated with regions of strong feature activity. The operator no longer treats all rows uniformly; instead, a subset of rows carries significantly higher importance due to weighting.

This leads to an effective low-dimensional structure in the measurement space, where most of the informative content is concentrated in a smaller number of dominant modes.

9.5 Implications for Sketching

The effectiveness of randomized sketching depends critically on the presence of compressible spectral structure.

- **Unweighted case:** Weak singular value decay \Rightarrow no dominant directions \Rightarrow behavior close to full rank \Rightarrow limited benefit from sketching.
- **Weighted case:** Stronger singular value decay \Rightarrow dominant directions exist \Rightarrow low-dimensional structure emerges \Rightarrow sketching efficiently preserves essential information.

Thus, weighting and sketching act in a complementary manner: weighting induces structure in the operator spectrum, while sketching exploits this structure for dimensionality reduction.

9.6 Spectral Role of Operator Weighting

The unweighted operator is governed purely by mesh connectivity and exhibits no intrinsic feature sensitivity. In contrast, operator weighting introduces solution-dependent scaling that enhances spectral separation, leading to a more pronounced decay in the singular value spectrum. This spectral decay is essential for the success of randomized sketching in sparse recovery-based AMR. This construction is referred to as **operator-weighted scaling**, where solution-dependent feature magnitudes are used to induce adaptive weighting of the discrete operator.

10 Physics-Informed Classification via Residuals

The refinement decision can also be posed as a physics-informed classification problem. That is

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{cell } i \text{ requires refinement,} \\ 0, & \text{cell } i \text{ does not require refinement.} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

Instead of pre-computed labels, physics residuals (e.g., discrete Euler residual components) guide the classification, so large residuals indicate insufficient discretization (such that refinement is needed), and small residuals indicate adequate discretization (such that no refinement is required).

A simple scoring mechanism (combining a sigmoid output from a neural network with residual magnitudes) automatically highlights cells needing refinement. This approach is physics-informed and scalable to complex geometries without labeled datasets.

Figure 7: Schematic illustration of ML-based adaptive mesh refinement.

Figure 7 shows how we integrated the GNN training process into our overall pipeline as described in Figure 6.

10.1 Node Features and Graph Construction

Each mesh cell is represented by flux-derived features. Let $\mathbf{F}_x, \mathbf{G}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 4}$ denote the discrete approximations of the spatial derivatives of the flux functions, i.e., $\mathbf{F}_x \approx \partial \mathbf{F} / \partial x$ and $\mathbf{G}_y \approx \partial \mathbf{G} / \partial y$. The flux derivative components are stacked directly as input features as

$$\mathbf{X}_i = [\mathbf{F}_x, \mathbf{G}_y]_i \in \mathbb{R}^8, \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (31)$$

Thus, the mesh graph is composed of nodes (i.e., mesh cells), edges (i.e., adjacency between cells), and node features (i.e., flux derivatives).

10.2 Physics-Informed Scoring and Refinement Selection

The model is trained using a physics-informed loss that encourages refinement in regions with large PDE residuals [7]. For cell i , the residual is defined as

$$\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{F}_x^i + \mathbf{G}_y^i, \quad \mathbf{r}_i \in \mathbb{R}^4, \quad (32)$$

where \mathbf{r}_i represents the discrete PDE residual arising from the violation of the conservation relation $\mathbf{F}_x^i + \mathbf{G}_y^i = 0$ at the cell level due to numerical discretization. Here, \mathbf{F}_x^i and \mathbf{G}_y^i denote the per-cell vector-valued flux components associated with cell i .

The training objective combines a physics-weighted penalty with a soft constraint on the number of refined cells. During training, the model operates in a continuous relaxation of the binary refinement variable y_i via a sigmoid output layer. This allows gradients to propagate while maintaining compatibility with a discrete refinement interpretation.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - y_i) \frac{\|\mathbf{r}_i\|_2}{\max_j \|\mathbf{r}_j\|_2}, \quad (33)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{count}} = \lambda \left(\sum_{i=1}^N y_i - N_{\text{target}} \right)^2, \quad (34)$$

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{count}}. \quad (35)$$

The trained model produces continuous refinement scores $y_i \in (0, 1)$ via a sigmoid output layer, representing a relaxed form of the binary refinement indicator. These scores are subsequently projected into a discrete refinement set for mesh adaptation. The final discrete decision is obtained either via thresholding or top- N_{target} selection, depending on the imposed mesh budget constraint.

After inference, the refinement set is obtained by selecting the N_{target} cells with the highest predicted scores:

$$\mathcal{S} = \{i \mid y_i \text{ is among the top } N_{\text{target}}\}. \quad (36)$$

This selection step acts as a deterministic projection from continuous scores to a fixed-budget discrete refinement decision, ensuring consistency with the target mesh resolution.

11 Preliminary Study: Graph-Based Refinement Baselines

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed physics-informed refinement principle, we first conduct a preliminary study using two standard graph neural network architectures: a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) and a Graph Attention Network (GAT) [8]. This study is intended as a baseline evaluation before proceeding to the full-scale detailed analysis presented in the subsequent section.

11.1 Graph Convolutional Network (GCN)

We use a simple GCN with 2 layers, each containing 175 hidden neurons. Each layer is followed by instance normalization and a ReLU activation. The final layer projects node embeddings to a scalar score, followed by a sigmoid activation with sharpening factor $\beta = 10$:

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(0)} = \mathbf{X}_i, \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(1)} = \text{ReLU}(\text{InstanceNorm}(\text{GCNConv}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(0)}))), \quad (38)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(2)} = \text{ReLU}(\text{InstanceNorm}(\text{GCNConv}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(1)}))), \quad (39)$$

$$y_i = \sigma(\beta \text{FC}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(2)})). \quad (40)$$

Here, $y_i \in [0, 1]$ represents the predicted refinement score for each cell and β controls the sharpness of the sigmoid, improving separation between refinement and non-refinement regions.

11.2 Graph Attention Network (GAT)

The GAT model consists of 2 layers with multi-head attention (4 heads per layer) [9]. Each head has 16 hidden neurons. Residual connections are incorporated whenever the input and output feature dimensions are compatible; in cases of mismatch, a linear projection is used to ensure dimensional consistency, together with instance normalization and ELU activations:

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(0)} = \mathbf{X}_i, \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(l+1)} = \text{ELU}(\text{InstanceNorm}(\text{GATConv}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(l)})) + \mathbf{h}_i^{(l)}), \quad l = 0, 1, \quad (42)$$

$$y_i = \sigma(\beta \text{FC}(\mathbf{h}_i^{(2)})). \quad (43)$$

Both models are trained under identical conditions to ensure a fair comparison of architecture effects under the same physics-informed objective.

11.3 Model Complexity and Training Results

The total number of trainable parameters for each model is summarized below:

Table 1: Model complexity and training performance for baseline study.

Model	Total Parameters	Final Training Loss
GCN	32,551	0.004893
GAT	5,057	0.004269

All models are implemented using the PyTorch framework [10] together with PyTorch Geometric [11], enabling efficient computation of graph convolutions and attention operations.

11.4 Interpretation

Despite having fewer parameters, the GAT achieves a slightly lower training loss, suggesting more efficient utilization of model capacity under the same physics-informed objective in this setting. However, this preliminary study does not yet assess generalization behavior, which is addressed in the detailed study in the following section.

12 Training Setup

12.1 Mesh Generation and Dataset Selection

The training dataset consists of a single mesh generated from one simulation, constructed using a sparse adaptive mesh generation procedure that concentrates resolution in regions of high complexity, such as discontinuities and sharp gradients. The mesh is produced using a combination of sparse recovery (OMP), randomized sketching (Rademacher matrix), VertexGrad operator, and operator-weighted scaling. This single, most challenging configuration is selected from multiple candidates to expose the model to a wide range of structural patterns, thereby improving generalization to unseen scenarios.

12.2 Hyperparameter Tuning

To ensure a fair and systematic comparison between GCN and GAT, we performed a complete grid search over a compact predefined hyperparameter space. The tuning procedure was applied independently to both architectures under identical experimental conditions.

In terms of hyperparameters, we let $L \in \{2, 4\}$ denotes the number of layers, $H \in \{16, 64\}$ denotes the number of hidden units (neurons) per layer, $\sigma \in \{\text{ReLU}, \text{ELU}\}$ denotes the activation function, and $K \in \{2, 4\}$ denotes the number of attention heads (used only for GAT).

We looped over the hyperparameter sets for fine-tuning and selected those that achieve the lowest training loss under the given physics-informed objective, evaluated on the single available training dataset.

The selected hyperparameters are $L = 4$, $H = 16$, $\sigma = \text{ELU}$ for the GCN model, and are $L = 2$, $H = 64$, $\sigma = \text{ELU}$, $K = 2$ for the GAT model.

13 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Annealed Mass Constraint

This loss modification defines a physics-informed, self-supervised learning framework in which residual magnitudes provide a physics-based signal to identify discontinuity regions on the mesh, and the resulting model produces a hierarchy of nested candidate sets that progressively concentrate around the discontinuity.

13.1 Setup

Based on the physics-informed loss described in 10.2, we proposed a modified version of it to improve the model performance.

Let

$$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}) \quad (44)$$

denote the computational mesh represented as a graph, where \mathcal{V} is the set of nodes (cells) and \mathcal{E} is the set of edges encoding adjacency relationships.

Let

$$N = |\mathcal{V}| \quad (45)$$

be the total number of cells.

Each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is associated with a feature vector \mathbf{x}_i , and we denote by \mathbf{X} the collection of all node features. A GNN is used to define a parametric scoring function

$$y_i = f_\theta(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{G})_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (46)$$

where θ denotes the model parameters, and

$$y_i \in (0, 1) \quad (47)$$

represents the refinement score assigned to cell i . Larger values of y_i indicate higher priority for mesh refinement.

We know that the physics-based residual quantity for each cell i is

$$\mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{F}_x^i + \mathbf{G}_y^i \quad (\text{discrete PDE residual}) \quad (48)$$

where \mathbf{F}_x^i and \mathbf{G}_y^i are flux derivatives computed from the governing equations. So, the residual magnitude is

$$\hat{r}_i = \|\mathbf{r}_i\|_2. \quad (49)$$

To ensure scale invariance across the mesh, we normalize the residuals as follows:

$$\tilde{r}_i = \frac{\hat{r}_i}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \hat{r}_j}. \quad (50)$$

By construction, $\tilde{r}_i \in [0, 1]$ for all i .

13.2 Loss Function Recall

At training step t , we define the loss function as

$$\mathcal{L}^{(t)}(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - y_i) \tilde{r}_i + \lambda \left(\sum_{i=1}^N y_i - \rho_t N \right)^2. \quad (51)$$

The loss consists of the physics-based term and the count regularization term.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - y_i) \tilde{r}_i. \quad (52)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{count}} = \lambda \left(\sum_{i=1}^N y_i - \rho_t N \right)^2, \quad (53)$$

where $\rho_t \in (0, 1)$ is a time-dependent target ratio.

This term constrains the total refinement mass $\sum_{i=1}^N y_i$ to be close to $\rho_t N$. Since $y_i \in (0, 1)$, this quantity can be interpreted as a soft approximation of the number of selected cells.

13.3 Annealing Schedule

The target ratio ρ_t is defined as a time-dependent function that decreases monotonically during training. Specifically, we consider

$$\rho_t = \begin{cases} 0.3 - 0.2 \cdot \frac{t}{T}, & \text{if } t \leq T, \\ 0.1, & \text{if } t > T, \end{cases} \quad (54)$$

where T is a predefined annealing horizon (e.g., $T = 500$ epochs).

Thus, ρ_t decreases linearly from 0.3 to 0.1 over the first T training steps, and remains fixed thereafter.

13.4 OMP-Informed Prior Assumption

The choice of the initial ratio $\rho_0 = 0.3$ is motivated by the structure of the adaptive mesh generated by the OMP method. Empirically, the adaptive mesh exhibits a concentration of fine cells near discontinuities. We formalize this as the following assumption:

$$(A1) \quad \exists \mathcal{D} \subset \mathcal{V} \quad \text{such that} \quad |\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N, \quad (55)$$

where \mathcal{D} denotes the set of cells located near the discontinuity.

Thus, approximately 30% of the cells belong to a fine-mesh region that contains the discontinuity. The initial value $\rho_0 = 0.3$ is chosen to match this empirical structure.

13.5 Interpretation

The model outputs scores $\{y_i\}_{i=1}^N$, which induce a ranking over the nodes. For any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, define the set

$$\mathcal{C}_\alpha = \{i \in \mathcal{V} : y_i \text{ is among the top } \alpha N \text{ values}\}. \quad (56)$$

These sets represent the top-ranked nodes according to the model.

During training, the annealing of ρ_t will likely induce a hierarchy of nested sets:

$$\mathcal{C}_{0.07} \subseteq \mathcal{C}_{0.1} \subseteq \mathcal{C}_{0.3}. \quad (57)$$

More specifically, $\mathcal{C}_{0.3}$ corresponds to a coarse candidate region, which is expected to align with the OMP-generated fine-mesh region containing the discontinuity; $\mathcal{C}_{0.1}$ corresponds to a refined prediction region, representing the final selection budget used in practice; $\mathcal{C}_{0.07}$ corresponds to a high-confidence core region, which empirically aligns closely with the discontinuity.

13.6 Coarse-to-Fine Learning Phases

The annealing strategy induces a two-phase learning process:

Phase I (coarse localization). When $\rho_t \approx 0.3$, the constraint

$$\sum_{i=1}^N y_i \approx 0.3N \quad (58)$$

encourages the model to distribute score mass over a relatively large subset of nodes. This promotes identification of a broad region containing the discontinuity:

$$\mathcal{C}_{0.3} \approx \mathcal{D}. \quad (59)$$

Phase II (fine localization). As ρ_t decreases toward 0.1, the model is forced to concentrate the score mass onto a smaller subset:

$$\mathcal{C}_{0.1} \subset \mathcal{C}_{0.3}. \quad (60)$$

This results in a sharper localization of the most relevant cells.

13.7 Empirical Reliability and Limitation

In addition to assumption (A1), we observe empirically that:

$$(A2) \quad \mathcal{C}_{0.07} \subseteq \mathcal{D} \quad (\text{up to negligible violations in practice}). \quad (61)$$

That is, the top 7% of predicted cells are predominantly contained within the discontinuity region with rare outliers. The remaining cells in

$$\mathcal{C}_{0.1} \setminus \mathcal{C}_{0.07} \quad (62)$$

form a buffer region that may include a small number of outliers.

13.8 Optimization

The loss function can be interpreted as a soft relaxation of a constrained optimization problem. Ignoring normalization constants, the objective is equivalent to

$$\max_{y \in [0,1]^N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \tilde{r}_i \quad \text{subject to} \quad \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \approx \rho_t N. \quad (63)$$

This formulation seeks to allocate a limited total score mass $\rho_t N$ to nodes with the largest residual values. In the limit, this objective can be interpreted as encouraging a solution that

approximates selection of nodes with the largest residual magnitudes, subject to the soft budget constraint.

Top 30% node predictions at n^{th} epoch (left) and $(n + k)^{\text{th}}$ epoch (right). This illustrates the difference between the original model and the trained model.

14 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-Model High-Precision Ensemble Approach

14.1 Motivation and Main Idea

In the previous extension, the model was trained so that the final prediction budget was gradually reduced from 30% of the mesh nodes to 10% of the mesh nodes. The purpose of this design was to first identify a broad region containing the discontinuity and then gradually concentrate the predictions onto a smaller subset.

Empirically, the top 7% of predicted nodes were highly reliable and were consistently located in the discontinuity region. The nodes ranked between 7% and 10% may include some outliers outside the discontinuity region.

This creates a precision–coverage tradeoff. If only the top 5% or top 7% of predictions are used, then the selected nodes are highly accurate, but the selected set may not cover the entire discontinuity region. On the other hand, if the top 10% of predictions are used, the coverage is improved, but some outliers may appear.

To address this issue, we propose a second extension based on multiple sub-models [12]. Instead of training one model to directly predict a relatively large fraction of the mesh, we train many sub-models, where each sub-model predicts only a very small fraction of nodes, for example the top 3%, top 1%, or even smaller. The reason for doing so is that when the prediction fraction is sufficiently small, the selected nodes have much higher probability of lying inside the discontinuity region. The final prediction set is then formed by combining the outputs of all sub-models.

The central idea is that each sub-model acts as a high-precision local detector of a small subset of discontinuity nodes. By taking the union of the predictions from many such sub-models, one can gradually increase the total coverage of the discontinuity region while maintaining very low outlier rate.

This extension is naturally interpreted as a *coverage-based ensemble method* over the discontinuity region.

14.2 Setup

Based on the OMP adaptive mesh, we make the empirical assumption that this region occupies approximately 30% of the mesh

$$|\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N. \quad (64)$$

The meaning of this assumption is that roughly 30% of all mesh cells belong to the fine-grid region surrounding the discontinuity. This 30% does not need to be exact; rather, it provides a geometric prior on the approximate size of the region of interest.

Suppose that we train M sub-models. The index

$$m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\} \quad (65)$$

will always denote the sub-model number.

For each sub-model m , let

$$f_{\theta_m}(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{G}) \quad (66)$$

denote the graph neural network with parameter vector θ_m , applied to node features \mathbf{X} and graph \mathcal{G} . For each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the m -th sub-model produces a refinement score

$$y_i^{(m)} = f_{\theta_m}(\mathbf{X}, \mathcal{G})_i. \quad (67)$$

Here, i denotes the node index; m denotes the sub-model index; $y_i^{(m)}$ is the score assigned by sub-model m to node i ; larger values of $y_i^{(m)}$ indicate that node i is considered more likely to belong to the discontinuity region by sub-model m .

For simplicity, one may assume

$$y_i^{(m)} \in (0, 1), \quad (68)$$

although the exact score range is not essential as long as the scores induce an ordering over the nodes.

14.3 Top- q Selection by Each Sub-Model

Let

$$q \in (0, 1) \quad (69)$$

denote the fraction of nodes predicted by each individual sub-model. For example, if one chooses $q = 0.03$, then each sub-model predicts only the top 3% of the mesh nodes. If one chooses $q = 0.01$, then each sub-model predicts only the top 1%.

For each sub-model m , define the selected set

$$\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} = \left\{ i \in \mathcal{V} : y_i^{(m)} \text{ is among the top } qN \text{ scores of sub-model } m \right\}, \quad (70)$$

where the superscript (m) indicates that the set is produced by sub-model m ; the subscript q indicates that only the top q fraction of nodes is selected.

By definition,

$$|\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}| = qN \quad (71)$$

if qN is an integer. If qN is not an integer, one can replace it by $\lfloor qN \rfloor$ or $\lceil qN \rceil$ without changing the theory in any essential way.

Thus, each sub-model predicts a small set of exactly qN nodes.

14.4 High-Precision Assumption for Small Prediction Budgets

The proposed method relies on the empirical observation that when each sub-model predicts only a very small fraction of nodes, its predictions are highly accurate. In mathematical terms, for sufficiently small q , the selected set $\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}$ is expected to lie almost entirely inside the discontinuity region \mathcal{D} .

This can be expressed using the precision ratio

$$\text{Prec}\left(\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}\right) = \frac{|\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \cap \mathcal{D}|}{|\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}|}, \quad (72)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \cap \mathcal{D}$ is the subset of nodes selected by sub-model m that truly lie in the discontinuity region; $|\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \cap \mathcal{D}|$ is the number of correct predictions made by sub-model m ; $|\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}|$ is the total number of nodes predicted by sub-model m .

The high-precision assumption means that

$$\text{Prec}\left(\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}\right) \approx 1 \quad (73)$$

for sufficiently small q . In the strongest idealized form, one may write

$$\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \subseteq \mathcal{D} \quad \text{for all } m. \quad (74)$$

The exact inclusion above is an idealization. In practice, the intended meaning is that the outlier rate becomes negligible when each sub-model predicts only a very small top fraction.

14.5 Why Small q Improves Precision

The role of the parameter q is central. If each sub-model is forced to select only a very small number of nodes, then it tends to retain only the most confident candidates. Empirically, these highly ranked nodes are much more likely to belong to the discontinuity region. Therefore, a smaller q empirically tends to yield higher precision. However, a smaller q also means that each individual sub-model covers only a smaller portion of the discontinuity region.

This creates a second precision–coverage tradeoff, but now at the level of the individual sub-model.

The ensemble idea resolves this tradeoff by using many sub-models with small q , so that each sub-model remains high-precision, while the union of their outputs increases the overall coverage.

14.6 Ensemble Prediction by Set Union

The final ensemble prediction after M sub-models is defined as the union of their selected sets:

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} = \bigcup_{m=1}^M \mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}. \quad (75)$$

where the subscript “ens” stands for ensemble; the superscript (M) indicates that the ensemble is built from the first M sub-models.

A node belongs to $\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)}$ if and only if it is selected by at least one of the M sub-models.

The number of unique predicted nodes is therefore

$$\left| \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \right|. \quad (76)$$

This quantity represents the total distinct coverage obtained by the ensemble.

14.7 Bounded-Coverage Property

Under the high-precision assumption that each $\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}$ lies approximately inside \mathcal{D} , the ensemble union also lies approximately inside \mathcal{D} . In the idealized exact case,

$$\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \subseteq \mathcal{D} \quad \text{for all } m \quad (77)$$

implies

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} = \bigcup_{m=1}^M \mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \subseteq \mathcal{D}. \quad (78)$$

As a consequence, in the idealized zero-false-positive regime,

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \subseteq \mathcal{D}. \quad (79)$$

In practice, this inclusion holds only approximately due to small but nonzero out-of-region selections. Accordingly, the ensemble size is expected to satisfy

$$\left| \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \right| \lesssim |\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N, \quad (80)$$

up to negligible deviations.

This inequality provides an approximate upper bound under the high-precision regime. It indicates that, as long as out-of-region predictions remain negligible, the total number of distinct predicted nodes is expected to remain close to the size of the discontinuity region.

This is precisely the sense in which the ensemble saturates near the true discontinuity region.

14.8 Duplication and Nonlinear Growth of Coverage

Although each sub-model predicts qN nodes, the total number of distinct nodes in the ensemble is generally much smaller than the sum of all predictions across sub-models. Indeed,

$$\sum_{m=1}^M |\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}| = MqN \quad (81)$$

counts all predictions with duplication, whereas

$$\left| \bigcup_{m=1}^M \mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \right| \quad (82)$$

counts only distinct nodes.

Because different sub-models may predict many of the same nodes, the union size does not grow linearly with M . This duplication effect is not a defect; rather, it reflects the fact that some nodes are more consistently detected than others. The repeated selection of the same node across many sub-models indicates that this node is a highly stable member of the discontinuity region.

14.9 Coverage Interpretation

The set union interpretation leads naturally to a notion of coverage. Define the coverage ratio of the ensemble with respect to the discontinuity region by

$$\text{Cov}^{(M)} = \frac{|\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \cap \mathcal{D}|}{|\mathcal{D}|}, \quad (83)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \cap \mathcal{D}$ is the subset of discontinuity nodes that have been covered by at least one of the first M sub-models; $|\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \cap \mathcal{D}|$ is the number of such covered discontinuity nodes; $|\mathcal{D}|$ is the total number of discontinuity nodes.

Thus, $\text{Cov}^{(M)}$ measures how much of the true discontinuity region has been recovered by the ensemble. Under the idealized exact-containment assumption

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \subseteq \mathcal{D}, \quad (84)$$

the coverage ratio simplifies to

$$\text{Cov}^{(M)} = \frac{|\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)}|}{|\mathcal{D}|}. \quad (85)$$

Therefore, increasing the number of sub-models increases the ensemble coverage until it approaches the full discontinuity region.

14.10 Statistical Viewpoint

To formulate the asymptotic behavior in a statistical way, define the indicator random variable

$$Z_i^{(m)} = \mathbf{1}\{i \in \mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}\}, \quad (86)$$

where $\mathbf{1}\{\cdot\}$ denotes the indicator function.

Thus $Z_i^{(m)} = 1$ if node i is selected by sub-model m , and $Z_i^{(m)} = 0$ otherwise.

For a fixed node i , define

$$p_i = \mathbb{P}\left(Z_i^{(m)} = 1\right). \quad (87)$$

The number p_i is the probability that node i is selected by a generic sub-model. The value of p_i depends on whether the node belongs to the discontinuity region. In particular, if $i \in \mathcal{D}$, then p_i is expected to be positive and possibly large; if $i \notin \mathcal{D}$, then p_i is expected to be very small, ideally zero.

Now consider the event that node i is selected by at least one of the first M sub-models. This event is

$$\left\{i \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)}\right\} = \bigcup_{m=1}^M \{Z_i^{(m)} = 1\}. \quad (88)$$

To obtain a tractable approximation, we adopt a conditional independence assumption across sub-models. Specifically, we assume that for each node i , the selection events $\{Z_i^{(m)}\}_{m=1}^M$ are approximately independent and share a common marginal probability p_i . This assumption is heuristic and serves to capture the aggregate behavior of the ensemble under weak dependence between sub-models.

Under this approximation, the probability that node i is selected by at least one of the M sub-models is given by

$$\mathbb{P}\left(i \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)}\right) = 1 - (1 - p_i)^M. \quad (89)$$

This expression should be interpreted as a heuristic estimate capturing ensemble aggregation behavior under weak dependence between sub-models.

This expression immediately implies that if $p_i > 0$, then

$$1 - (1 - p_i)^M \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } M \rightarrow \infty; \quad (90)$$

If $p_i = 0$, then

$$1 - (1 - p_i)^M = 0 \quad \text{for all } M. \quad (91)$$

Therefore, nodes that have positive probability of being selected by a high-precision sub-model will eventually be covered by the ensemble with probability tending to one, while nodes that are never selected remain permanently excluded.

14.11 Asymptotic Coverage of the Discontinuity Region

The previous calculation suggests a natural asymptotic convergence statement. Suppose for every node $i \in \mathcal{D}$,

$$p_i = \mathbb{P}(Z_i^{(m)} = 1) > 0; \quad (92)$$

and for every node $i \notin \mathcal{D}$,

$$p_i = 0 \quad \text{or at least } p_i \text{ is negligible}; \quad (93)$$

The sub-models are sufficiently diverse so that the selections across different m are not perfectly identical.

Then for each $i \in \mathcal{D}$,

$$\mathbb{P}(i \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)}) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } M \rightarrow \infty. \quad (94)$$

In words, every true discontinuity node is eventually covered by the ensemble with probability tending to one. Consequently, the ensemble union approaches the discontinuity region itself.

A natural set-level formulation of this idea is

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \text{ is expected to converge in coverage toward } \mathcal{D} \quad \text{as } M \rightarrow \infty, \quad (95)$$

where the convergence is understood in the sense of statistical coverage or set recovery, not necessarily as a deterministic equality for every finite M .

A more explicit way to express this is through the symmetric difference

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \triangle \mathcal{D} = \left(\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \setminus \mathcal{D} \right) \cup \left(\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \right). \quad (96)$$

The symmetric difference measures the discrepancy between the ensemble prediction and the true discontinuity region. If the false-positive part

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \setminus \mathcal{D} \quad (97)$$

remains negligible and the missed-discontinuity part

$$\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \quad (98)$$

shrinks to the empty set as M increases, then

$$\left| \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \triangle \mathcal{D} \right| \rightarrow 0 \quad (99)$$

in a normalized or probabilistic sense. This is the rigorous mathematical meaning of saying that the ensemble predictions become infinitely close to the discontinuity region.

14.12 Interpretation of the Asymptotic Guarantee

It is important to state carefully what kind of guarantee is and is not being claimed.

The asymptotic statement does *not* mean that for any finite number of sub-models the ensemble exactly equals the discontinuity region. Instead, it means that under suitable statistical assumptions. Each true discontinuity node has a positive chance of being selected by some sub-model. False positives remain negligible relative to the size of the discontinuity region. Therefore, as the number of sub-models grows, the ensemble increasingly covers the true discontinuity region.

Thus, the proposed extension admits an *asymptotic statistical set-recovery guarantee* under the stated assumptions.

Assume that each sub-model selects only high-precision nodes, so that out-of-region predictions are negligible, and assume that every node in the discontinuity region has positive probability of being selected by an individual sub-model. Then, as the number of sufficiently diverse sub-models tends to infinity, the ensemble union converges in coverage to the discontinuity region.

This is the mathematically correct version of the claimed asymptotic guarantee.

14.13 Relation Between the Ensemble Size and the 30% Region

Because the discontinuity region contains only about 30% of all nodes, the ensemble prediction cannot expand indefinitely. Even if one uses infinitely many sub-models, the union cannot meaningfully grow beyond the true region, because every individual high-precision prediction is assumed to lie inside that region.

Therefore, under the idealized assumption that each sub-model prediction lies almost entirely within the discontinuity region (i.e., negligible false-positive rate at the level of the union), we have

$$\left| \mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} \right| \lesssim |\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N, \quad (100)$$

This should be interpreted as an approximate upper bound that holds in the regime where out-of-region predictions are negligible relative to the size of \mathcal{D} . Hence, the limiting prediction set is naturally constrained by the geometry and scale of the discontinuity region rather than growing unbounded with M .

This explains why using more sub-models does not generate arbitrary growth in the number of predicted nodes. Instead, it refines the *coverage* of the same underlying region.

14.14 Tunable Design Parameters

The proposed method contains two main design parameters. One is the number of sub-models M , and the other is the per-sub-model prediction fraction q .

The parameter q controls the selection budget of each sub-model and thus influences the precision of the predicted set. Empirically, reducing q tends to increase precision, since only the most highly ranked nodes are retained, which are more likely to lie in the discontinuity region. However, this comes at the cost of reduced coverage per sub-model, implying that more sub-models are required to achieve full coverage of \mathcal{D} .

This should be understood as an empirical trend observed in OMP-guided adaptive mesh structures rather than a strict monotonic guarantee.

The parameter M controls the total ensemble coverage. Larger M increases the number of distinct nodes predicted by the ensemble. However, due to overlap, the coverage increase eventually saturates near $|\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N$.

Thus, the pair (M, q) determines the balance between local precision and global coverage.

14.15 Interpretations

The second extension can now be summarized formally as follows.

Let $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ denote the discontinuity region, with

$$|\mathcal{D}| \approx 0.3N. \quad (101)$$

Train M sub-models, and let each sub-model m predict only a very small top- q subset

$$\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)} \subseteq \mathcal{V}. \quad (102)$$

Assume that for sufficiently small q , each $\mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}$ is highly accurate and lies almost entirely in \mathcal{D} . Define the ensemble prediction as the union

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{ens}}^{(M)} = \bigcup_{m=1}^M \mathcal{S}_q^{(m)}. \quad (103)$$

Then we can say that each sub-model contributes a small, high-precision subset of discontinuity nodes. The union over many sub-models increases the total coverage of the discontinuity region. The total ensemble prediction remains bounded by the size of the discontinuity region itself. Under suitable statistical assumptions, the ensemble converges asymptotically in coverage to the discontinuity region as $M \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, the proposed method provides a mathematically interpretable mechanism for simultaneously achieving high precision at the sub-model level and extensive coverage at the ensemble level.

15 Error Analysis

To quantify the accuracy of the numerical solution on adaptive meshes, we consider area-weighted error norms between the numerical solution on the adaptive mesh and a reference solution. Although the solver computes all conserved variables, the analysis focuses exclusively on the **density**, denoted by \mathcal{U} :

$$\mathcal{U} = \rho, \quad (104)$$

which is the quantity monitored by the solver's RMS convergence criterion.

15.1 Area-Weighted Error Norms

Area-weighted error norms are defined in the literature [13] and are computed between the numerical solution on the adaptive mesh and a reference solution obtained on a very fine uniform mesh. Let $\mathcal{U}_{\text{adaptive}}$ and \mathcal{U}_{ref} denote the density fields on the adaptive and reference meshes, respectively, and let A_i denote the area of the i -th adaptive cell.

The reference solution is mapped onto the adaptive mesh using a centroid-based aggregation strategy, where each reference cell is uniquely assigned to a single adaptive cell based on nearest-centroid proximity, forming a complete partition of the reference mesh (Figure 8). Multiple reference cells may map to the same adaptive cell, leading to an area-weighted averaging that preserves integral consistency.

The area-weighted L_1 and L_2 error norms are defined as:

$$\text{Area-weighted } L_1 \text{ error: } \|\mathcal{U}_{\text{adaptive}} - \mathcal{U}_{\text{ref}}\|_{L_1} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}} A_i |\mathcal{U}_i^{\text{adaptive}} - \mathcal{U}_i^{\text{interp}}|}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}} A_i}, \quad (105)$$

$$\text{Area-weighted } L_2 \text{ error: } \|\mathcal{U}_{\text{adaptive}} - \mathcal{U}_{\text{ref}}\|_{L_2} = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}} A_i (\mathcal{U}_i^{\text{adaptive}} - \mathcal{U}_i^{\text{interp}})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}} A_i} \right)^{1/2}.$$

Here, $\mathcal{U}_i^{\text{interp}}$ denotes the reference solution interpolated onto the i -th adaptive cell.

15.2 Reference Solution

The reference solution \mathcal{U}_{ref} is obtained by solving the Euler equations on a very fine uniform mesh, assumed to represent a **highly resolved reference solution with negligible discretization error**. Each reference cell is associated with a unique adaptive cell via centroid-based nearest-centroid assignment, inducing a partition of the reference mesh.

Assumptions:

- Interpolation error from the reference to adaptive mesh is negligible compared to discretization error.
- Density is representative of the overall solution error.
- Shocks are sufficiently resolved on the reference mesh.

15.3 Conservative Interpolation

To account for differences in resolution between meshes, the reference solution is mapped onto the adaptive mesh using a conservative centroid-based projection strategy. For each adaptive cell, the interpolated density is computed as an area-weighted average:

$$\mathcal{U}_i^{\text{interp}} = \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}(i)} A_j^{\text{ref}} \mathcal{U}_j^{\text{ref}}}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{M}(i)} A_j^{\text{ref}}}, \quad (106)$$

where $\mathcal{M}(i)$ denotes the set of reference cells assigned to adaptive cell i .

The sets $\{\mathcal{M}(i)\}_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}}$ form a disjoint partition of the reference mesh, i.e.,

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^{N_{\text{adaptive}}} \mathcal{M}(i) = \Omega_{\text{ref}}, \quad \mathcal{M}(i) \cap \mathcal{M}(j) = \emptyset \text{ for } i \neq j. \quad (107)$$

This aggregation is conservative at the discrete level since the reference mesh is fully partitioned into disjoint sets $\mathcal{M}(i)$, ensuring that finite-volume summation preserves integral quantities exactly under the area-weighted averaging procedure.

15.4 Nearest-Neighbor Interpretation

Although the aggregation is defined through a partitioning of the reference mesh, it can equivalently be viewed as a nearest-centroid assignment in physical space, where each reference cell is associated with the closest adaptive centroid under the Euclidean metric. This provides a geometric interpretation of the mapping induced by the adaptive mesh structure.

Figure 8: Conservative mapping of reference mesh centroids onto adaptive mesh centroids.

15.5 Convergence Criterion

The iterative solver monitors convergence using the RMS change in density:

$$\text{RMS}_{\mathcal{U}}^k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\text{cells}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{cells}}} (\mathcal{U}_i^k - \mathcal{U}_i^{k-1})^2}. \quad (108)$$

The solution is considered converged when $\text{RMS}_{\mathcal{U}}^k$ falls below a prescribed tolerance (set to 1×10^{-13}), justifying the use of density as the primary quantity for error analysis.

16 Geometry and Problem Setup

The computational domain is a two-dimensional, approximately rectangular region defined as:

$$x \in [-1.0, 1.0], \quad y \in [0.0, 1.5]. \quad (109)$$

A piecewise-linear wedge is placed along the bottom boundary, consisting of two segments:

- **Left wedge:** induces a shock with angle $\theta_1 = 15^\circ$.
- **Right wedge:** induces a shock with angle $\theta_2 = 15^\circ, 8^\circ, \text{ or } -8^\circ$, depending on the case.

This setup leads to the formation of discontinuities in two-dimensional Euler flows under the boundary conditions specified below. The computational configuration is informed by the inviscid wedge problem described in the SU2 tutorial [14].

17 Boundary Conditions

The supersonic 2D Euler flow over the wedge in a channel is defined with the following boundary conditions. The domain boundaries are labeled as *Left* (inlet), *Right* (outlet), *Wedge* (solid wall), *Top*, and *Bottom* (channel walls).

Figure 9: Computational domain for the 2D Euler wedge problem. The left wedge has an angle of $\theta_1 = 15^\circ$ and the right wedge angle θ_2 varies between 15° , 8° , and -8° .

17.1 Inlet

A supersonic inlet is applied at the left boundary, where the flow state is specified consistently with the free-stream Mach number, pressure, and temperature:

$$u_\infty = 694.4 \text{ m/s}, \quad v_\infty = 0, \quad w_\infty = 0, \quad (110)$$

$$p_\infty = 10^5 \text{ Pa}, \quad T_\infty = 300 \text{ K}, \quad M_\infty = 2.0. \quad (111)$$

17.2 Walls

The solid walls, including the wedge and the top and bottom channel boundaries, are treated as inviscid Euler walls. The flow satisfies the no-penetration condition at these boundaries:

$$\vec{V} \cdot \hat{n} = 0, \quad (112)$$

where \vec{V} is the velocity vector and \hat{n} is the local unit normal to the wall. This enforces zero normal velocity while allowing tangential slip along the wall.

17.3 Outlet

A pressure outlet is applied at the right boundary, where the static pressure is prescribed:

$$p_{\text{out}} = 10^4 \text{ Pa}. \quad (113)$$

This boundary condition is implemented in SU2 under a supersonic outlet configuration, where flow variables are extrapolated from the interior while enforcing the specified outlet pressure.

17.4 Remarks

- The inlet ensures supersonic flow enters the domain with the specified Mach number and thermodynamic state.
- Euler wall boundaries model inviscid slip flow around the wedge and channel walls.

- The outlet allows the flow to exit the domain, while enforcing the prescribed pressure in a manner consistent with SU2’s supersonic outlet formulation.

18 Mesh Generation and Refinement

The computational domain is discretized using unstructured triangular elements generated with `Gmsh` [15], which provides flexibility in representing complex geometries and supports field-driven mesh refinement based on prescribed indicators.

Mesh refinement is applied according to the following specifications:

- **Base characteristic length:** $l_c = 0.1$.
- **Adaptive local refinement:** optional point-based refinement around user-specified points or mesh vertices, typically near shock regions or regions with high solution gradients.

- **Element size limits:**

$$0.02 \leq \text{Element size} \leq 0.1. \tag{114}$$

- **Distance field range for refinement control:**

$$0.03 \leq \text{Distance} \leq 0.06. \tag{115}$$

The adaptive refinement is implemented using the `Distance` and `Threshold` fields in `Gmsh`, ensuring that regions with strong solution gradients are resolved accurately while avoiding unnecessary mesh refinement in smooth regions.

19 Mesh Refinement Results

This section presents the results of the proposed sparse recovery and learning-based mesh adaptation framework. The analysis is organized into two main components - sparse recovery performance under different operator modifications and machine learning-based refinement prediction - while the quantitative error assessment is presented in the subsequent section.

19.1 Sparse Recovery Results

This subsection evaluates the performance of the sparse recovery framework under different configurations of the sensing operator.

19.1.1 No Sketching or Scaling

In this case, the original full operator is used without any dimensionality reduction or weighting. The objective is to serve as a baseline for comparison against modified sensing strategies. The recovered solution is analyzed in terms of sparsity structure and recovery fidelity.

ℓ_0 : **Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)**

Figure 10 illustrates the active cells in the final adapted mesh obtained using OMP. The rows correspond to the operators: **Jump**, **VertexGrad**, and **CellGrad**. The three columns represent the wedge angles $\theta_2 = 15^\circ, 8^\circ, -8^\circ$. This figure highlights the influence of operator choice and wedge angle on active cell selection during sparse mesh adaptation.

Figure 10: OMP results for different operators (rows) and wedge angles θ_2 (columns). Selected cells are shown with green color for centroid-based selection and blue color for vertex-based selection.

For the **Jump** operator, both the secondary shock and expansion fan are clearly resolved, indicating that this operator effectively captures sharp, localized features. In contrast, the **VertexGrad** operator fails to resolve either the secondary shock or the expansion fan. The **CellGrad** operator shows only a small localized region over the expansion fan, suggesting partial but insufficient resolution of weaker features.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the choice of operator significantly affects OMP’s ability to resolve strong and weak flow features while maintaining sparsity in the adapted mesh. This indicates that sparsity is not only operator-dependent but also strongly influenced by the ability of the operator to represent discontinuous structures in a compressible form.

ℓ_0 : **Iterative Hard Thresholding (IHT)**

Figure 11 shows the active cells obtained using the IHT algorithm. Compared to OMP, IHT captures the secondary shock and expansion fan more effectively, with a finer distribution of active cells along these structures.

IHT solves a sparsity-constrained least-squares problem, minimizing the squared residual subject to a fixed sparsity level. Iterative updates use a step size based on the spectral bound of $\mathbf{D}^\top \mathbf{D}$, ensuring stable convergence.

The CellGrad operator behavior is consistent with OMP: weaker features are not fully resolved compared to Jump-based selection.

Figure 11: IHT results for different operators (rows) and wedge angles θ_2 (columns). Selected cells are shown with green color for centroid-based selection and blue color for vertex-based selection.

ℓ_0 : **Hard Thresholding Pursuit (HTP)**

Figure 12: HTP results for different operators (rows) and wedge angles θ_2 (columns). Selected cells are shown with green color for centroid-based selection and blue color for vertex-based selection.

Figure 12 shows the active cells obtained using the HTP algorithm. In several cases, convergence issues are observed, indicating reduced stability compared to OMP and IHT.

Overall, HTP shows weaker performance in capturing secondary shocks and expansion features,

particularly for more challenging configurations.

ℓ_1 : **FISTA**

Figure 13 shows the active cells obtained using the FISTA algorithm. FISTA captures secondary flow features more effectively than OMP, showing improved distribution along weaker structures.

The CellGrad operator primarily identifies dominant shocks, while Jump-based selection provides better overall coverage of flow features.

Figure 13: FISTA results for different operators (rows) and wedge angles θ_2 (columns). Selected cells are shown with green color for centroid-based selection and blue color for vertex-based selection.

19.1.2 Sketching without Scaling

In this study, we investigate the effect of applying random sketching without additional scaling of the operator. A sketching operator is applied to obtain a lower-dimensional representation of the full sensing matrix, with the objective of assessing whether sparse recovery structure and key flow features are preserved under compression.

We restrict the analysis to two representative methods: Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) as a greedy ℓ_0 -based method, and FISTA as a convex ℓ_1 -based method. These are chosen to represent two fundamentally different sparse recovery paradigms.

For each method, we consider two sketching strategies: Gaussian sketching and Rademacher sketching. Due to the behavior of sketching in this regime, the recovered solution often becomes highly dense, with a large fraction of cells being selected. As a result, two complementary visualization styles are required: one showing selected cells using centroid/vertex-based highlighting (green and blue markers respectively), and another showing the raw selection pattern without highlighting to better illustrate the overall mesh structure when sparsity is lost.

ℓ_0 : **Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)**

Figures 14–17 present the results obtained using OMP under sketching. We consider four configurations: Gaussian sketching with highlighted selection, Gaussian sketching without highlighting, Rademacher sketching with highlighted selection, and Rademacher sketching without highlighting.

For both **Jump** and **CellGrad** operators, the recovered solution becomes nearly fully dense, with almost all cells being selected. This indicates a collapse of sparsity structure under sketching, where the method loses its ability to localize refinement regions.

For the **VertexGrad** operator, a weak tendency to concentrate around discontinuities is observed; however, the selection remains scattered and includes significant activation in regions unrelated to physical flow features.

OMP with Gaussian sketching (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 14: OMP with Gaussian sketching (highlighted selection).

Figure 15: OMP with Gaussian sketching (raw mesh). Nearly all cells are selected, indicating loss of sparsity structure.

OMP with Rademacher sketching (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 16: OMP with Rademacher sketching (highlighted selection).

Figure 17: OMP with Rademacher sketching (raw mesh). Similar dense selection behavior is observed.

ℓ_1 : FISTA

Figures 18–21 show the results obtained using FISTA under sketching. Similar to OMP, the recovered solution becomes highly dense across both Gaussian and Rademacher sketching strategies.

In both cases, the method loses its ability to isolate shocks and expansion regions, and the refinement pattern becomes nearly uniform across the domain. This indicates that sketching without scaling destroys the sparsity-promoting structure of the ℓ_1 formulation in this setting.

FISTA with Gaussian sketching (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 18: FISTA with Gaussian sketching (highlighted selection).

Figure 19: FISTA with Gaussian sketching (raw mesh). Nearly full-domain activation is observed.

FISTA with Rademacher sketching (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 20: FISTA with Rademacher sketching (highlighted selection).

Figure 21: FISTA with Rademacher sketching (raw mesh). Similar loss of sparsity structure is observed.

Overall Observation

Across both ℓ_0 (OMP) and ℓ_1 (FISTA) methods, sketching without scaling leads to a collapse of sparsity structure. While OMP exhibits slight operator-dependent structure in limited cases, both methods ultimately produce highly dense selections, indicating that sketching alone is insufficient to preserve meaningful sparse recovery behavior in this framework.

19.1.3 Sketching with Scaling

In this study, we investigate the effect of combining random sketching with appropriate scaling of the operator. In contrast to the previous case, the operator is first scaled using the right-hand side of the governing equation before applying the sketching operator (as described in Section 9.3). This modification ensures that the compressed system retains information about the physical magnitude of the residuals.

As before, we consider two representative methods: Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) as a greedy ℓ_0 -based method, and FISTA as a convex ℓ_1 -based method. Both Gaussian and Rademacher sketching strategies are evaluated.

Unlike the unscaled case, the inclusion of scaling restores the sparsity structure of the recovered solution. The selected cells now concentrate around physically meaningful regions such as shocks and expansion fans, and the refinement patterns are consistent with those observed in the baseline (no-sketching) case.

ℓ_0 : Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)

Figures 22–25 present the results obtained using OMP with sketching and scaling. Four configurations are shown: Gaussian sketching with highlighted selection, Gaussian sketching without highlighting, Rademacher sketching with highlighted selection, and Rademacher sketching without highlighting.

In contrast to the sketching-only case, the recovered solution remains sparse and well-structured. For all operators, the selected cells align with key flow features. The **Jump** operator continues to sharply capture discontinuities, while **CellGrad** and **VertexGrad** show improved localization compared to the unscaled case. The refinement is no longer spread across the domain and instead focuses on physically relevant regions.

OMP with Gaussian sketching and scaling (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 22: OMP with Gaussian sketching and scaling (highlighted selection).

Figure 23: OMP with Gaussian sketching and scaling (raw mesh). Sparse and localized refinement is observed.

OMP with Rademacher sketching and scaling (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 24: OMP with Rademacher sketching and scaling (highlighted selection).

Figure 25: OMP with Rademacher sketching and scaling (raw mesh). Similar structured sparsity is preserved.

ℓ_1 : FISTA

Figures 26–29 show the results obtained using FISTA with sketching and scaling. As with OMP, both Gaussian and Rademacher sketching produce consistent and physically meaningful refinement patterns.

The recovered solution retains sparsity and clearly identifies shocks and expansion regions. Compared to the sketching-only case, the refinement is no longer uniformly distributed but instead concentrated in regions of high physical significance. This demonstrates that scaling restores the effectiveness of the ℓ_1 formulation under sketching.

FISTA with Gaussian sketching and scaling (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 26: FISTA with Gaussian sketching and scaling (highlighted selection).

Figure 27: FISTA with Gaussian sketching and scaling (raw mesh). Clear localization of refinement is observed.

FISTA with Rademacher sketching and scaling (highlighted selection and raw mesh)

Figure 28: FISTA with Rademacher sketching and scaling (highlighted selection).

Figure 29: FISTA with Rademacher sketching and scaling (raw mesh). Structured sparsity is consistently recovered.

Overall Observation

Across both ℓ_0 (OMP) and ℓ_1 (FISTA) methods, combining sketching with scaling successfully preserves the sparsity structure and restores physically meaningful refinement patterns. Unlike the sketching-only case, the methods consistently identify key flow features while maintaining a sparse set of selected cells. This demonstrates that proper scaling is essential for enabling effective compressed sensing in the context of adaptive mesh refinement.

19.1.4 Singular Value Spectrum Analysis

To further understand the behavior of sketching with and without scaling, we analyze the singular value spectrum of the sensing operator under both configurations. The objective is to examine how scaling affects the spectral structure, which in turn influences the performance of sparse recovery methods.

We consider two representative methods: Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) for the ℓ_0 formulation and FISTA for the ℓ_1 formulation. For each method, the singular value spectrum is computed for both unscaled (sketching only) and scaled (sketching with scaling) operators. All three wedge angles and operator choices (**Jump**, **VertexGrad**, and **CellGrad**) are included in the analysis.

ℓ_0 : Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP)

Figures 30 and 31 show the singular value spectrum of the operator used in OMP for the unweighted and weighted cases, respectively.

In the unweighted case, the singular value spectrum is relatively flat, indicating that the energy is distributed across many modes. This lack of decay suggests that the operator does not exhibit a dominant low-dimensional structure, making sparse recovery more difficult and less stable.

In contrast, the weighted case exhibits a rapidly decaying singular value spectrum, where the leading singular values dominate and the remaining modes decay quickly. This indicates that the operator effectively captures the dominant physical structures in a low-dimensional subspace, which is favorable for sparse recovery.

Figure 30: Singular value spectrum for OMP (unweighted case) across different operators and wedge angles. A relatively flat spectrum is observed.

Figure 31: Singular value spectrum for OMP (weighted case) across different operators and wedge angles. Rapid decay of singular values is observed.

ℓ_1 : FISTA

Figures 32 and 33 present the singular value spectrum for the FISTA formulation under unweighted and weighted configurations.

The same trend is observed as in the ℓ_0 case. The unweighted operator exhibits a flat spectrum, indicating the absence of dominant modes and a lack of compressibility. In contrast, the weighted operator shows a sharp decay in singular values, suggesting that the system becomes effectively low-rank.

This structural change explains the improved performance of sparse recovery methods when scaling is applied prior to sketching.

Figure 32: Singular value spectrum for FISTA (unweighted case). The spectrum remains relatively flat across configurations.

Figure 33: Singular value spectrum for FISTA (weighted case). A strong decay pattern is observed, indicating improved spectral structure.

Overall Observation

Across both ℓ_0 (OMP) and ℓ_1 (FISTA) formulations, the singular value spectrum clearly distinguishes the unweighted and weighted cases. The unweighted operator exhibits a flat spectrum, indicating poor compressibility and lack of dominant modes. In contrast, the weighted operator shows rapid spectral decay, revealing an underlying low-dimensional structure. This transition directly explains why sketching fails without scaling and becomes effective when combined with appropriate weighting.

19.1.5 Influence of Sketching Dimension

In this study, we investigate how varying the sketching dimension affects the behavior of the OMP (ℓ_0) method using Rademacher sketching. The sketching dimension is controlled via a *sketch factor*, which determines the number of rows retained in the sketched system. Two configurations are considered: unweighted (without operator scaling) and weighted (with operator-weighted scaling).

Figure 34 illustrates the effect of sketch dimension on the resulting refinement patterns. The top row corresponds to the weighted case, while the bottom row corresponds to the unweighted case, across different sketch factors.

Figure 34: OMP: Effect of sketch dimension on refinement patterns. Top: weighted case (operator-weighted scaling), showing consistent and structured refinement as the sketch dimension is reduced. Bottom: unweighted case, where refinement deteriorates and fails to capture key flow features at lower sketch dimensions.

In the weighted configuration, the refinement pattern remains stable as the sketch dimension is reduced. The selected cells continue to align with key flow features such as shocks and expansion regions. As the sketch factor decreases, the number of refined cells is gradually reduced, but the overall structure of the refinement remains consistent. This indicates that the method is able to maintain physically meaningful sparsity even under aggressive dimensionality reduction.

In contrast, the unweighted configuration exhibits significant degradation as the sketch dimension decreases. At higher sketch factors, some structure is still visible; however, as the sketch dimension is further reduced, the refinement becomes increasingly scattered and fails to capture the relevant flow features. In extreme cases, the selection becomes insufficient or misaligned with the underlying physical structures.

Overall, these results show that operator-weighted scaling plays a critical role in maintaining robust and consistent mesh adaptation under varying sketch dimensions. While the weighted formulation preserves structured and meaningful refinement patterns, the unweighted formulation becomes unreliable as the level of compression increases.

19.1.6 Effect of Perturbation Scaling Factor

In this study, we investigate the influence of the perturbation scaling factor on sparse recovery performance. The perturbation is introduced as a relative modification of the right-hand side,

$$\Delta \mathbf{B}_{\text{perturbed}} = \epsilon \mathbf{B},$$

where ϵ controls the magnitude of the perturbation. Two representative values are considered: $\epsilon = 0.01$ (small perturbation) and $\epsilon = 0.4$ (large perturbation). The analysis is restricted to the **Jump** operator with operator-weighted scaling.

We consider two representative methods: OMP (ℓ_0) and FISTA (ℓ_1), to assess the sensitivity of both greedy and convex sparse recovery approaches to perturbations.

Figure 35 shows the resulting refinement patterns. Across both methods, the refinement structures remain nearly unchanged as the perturbation scaling factor is increased from $\epsilon = 0.01$ to $\epsilon = 0.4$. The location and distribution of selected cells continue to align with the primary shock, secondary structures, and expansion regions.

The differences between the two perturbation levels are minimal and, in most cases, not visually distinguishable. This indicates that the sparse recovery process is largely insensitive to the magnitude of the perturbation once operator-weighted scaling is applied.

Overall, these results demonstrate that both OMP and FISTA exhibit strong robustness to perturbations in the right-hand side under the weighted formulation. The stability of the refinement patterns suggests that the operator-weighted scaling effectively regularizes the problem, making the recovery process resilient to moderate perturbations.

Figure 35: Effect of perturbation scaling factor ϵ on sparse refinement patterns using the Jump operator with operator-weighted scaling. From left to right: OMP (ℓ_0) with $\epsilon = 0.01$, OMP (ℓ_0) with $\epsilon = 0.4$, FISTA (ℓ_1) with $\epsilon = 0.01$, and FISTA (ℓ_1) with $\epsilon = 0.4$. The refinement patterns remain nearly identical across perturbation levels, indicating strong robustness.

19.2 Machine Learning Results

19.2.1 Preliminary Study: Graph-Based Refinement Baselines

This subsection presents a baseline evaluation of graph-based machine learning models for predicting refinement indicators (as described in Section 11). Two architectures are considered: a Graph Convolution Network (GCN) and a Graph Attention Network (GAT). Both models are trained on a single high-fidelity simulation corresponding to the adapted mesh at $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$, which contains representative shock and expansion structures.

The objective of this baseline study is to assess whether graph-based learning, trained on a single simulation case, can recover physically meaningful refinement patterns without access to multiple training configurations.

Figure 36 shows the predicted active cells for both models. Both GCN and GAT identify regions of elevated residual activity and produce refinement patterns consistent with dominant flow structures. The GAT exhibits slightly more localized responses in certain regions due to the attention mechanism, although the overall improvement over the GCN is modest.

Compared to classical sparse recovery methods, the learned models produce qualitatively consistent refinement regions but are less reliable in resolving fine-scale structures such as weak gradients and expansion fans. In contrast, ℓ_0 - and ℓ_1 -based sparse recovery methods (e.g., OMP, IHT, and FISTA) more consistently capture sharply localized flow features.

Figure 36: Active cells predicted by the ML models for the adapted mesh at $\theta_2 = -8^\circ, 8^\circ$, and 15° . Top: GCN predictions. Bottom: GAT predictions. Both models capture regions of elevated residual activity and align with dominant flow structures, while finer features such as expansion regions are less distinctly resolved compared to classical sparse recovery methods.

The performance of each model, measured using the physics-informed loss on the training simulation, is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Loss values for models trained on the adapted mesh at $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$.

Model	Loss
GCN	0.004893
GAT	0.004269

Overall, this baseline study shows that graph-based machine learning models can learn meaningful refinement indicators from a single high-fidelity simulation. However, their ability to resolve fine-scale flow structures remains limited compared to classical sparse recovery methods, which more consistently identify shocks and expansion features.

19.2.2 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Fine-tuned Hyperparameters

We selected the fine-tuned hyperparameters (as described in Section 12.2) for both GCN and GAT models, and directly applied the original physics-informed classification loss (as described in Section 10.2) to train the mesh data (as described in Section 12.1).

Figure 37: Mesh training results by GCNs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

Figure 38: Mesh training results by GATs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

The GCN model performance in Figure 37 is much worse than the GAT model performance in Figure 38. When $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$, GCN performs well. When $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$, the GCN is no longer able to perform well. However, GAT performs well on all three angle parameter values. This shows that GAT outperforms GCN when the original physics-informed classification loss is applied with fine-tuned hyperparameters. Note that both Figure 37 and Figure 38 are training performances, since the models are trained and used to predict on the same mesh data.

19.2.3 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-Model High-Precision Ensemble Approach

As described in Section 13 and Section 14, we proposed methods to modify the original physics-informed classification loss. We then retrain the GCN and GAT models using the same mesh data as the training set.

Figure 39: Improved mesh training results by ensemble-based GCNs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

Figure 40: Improved mesh training results by ensemble-based GATs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

In this case, Figure 39 shows that GCN works well for all three angle parameter values. Both Figure 39 and Figure 40 show better results than they did in Figure 37 and Figure 38.

However, both Figure 39 and Figure 40 can show the training performance of the GCN and GAT models only. The models are trained and evaluated on the same mesh data. We are interested in whether the trained model can still perform well when used to predict on different mesh data. To evaluate the testing performance of the GCN and GAT models, we use the same trained models but predict on a totally different mesh. This mesh data has a different angle parameter θ_2 and even a different discontinuity location.

Figure 41: Improved mesh testing results by ensemble-based GCNs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

Figure 42: Improved mesh testing results by ensemble-based GATs. The left is $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$; the middle figure is $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$; the right figure is $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$. Note that θ_2 indicates the angle parameter of the mesh.

As we observe in Figure 41 and Figure 42, both GCN and GAT models still perform well when trained on one mesh and evaluated on another. The trained models can still learn the pattern and identify the discontinuity region, despite the training and testing meshes differing in many aspects. This result shows a strong generalization and robustness of the proposed learning metric and training strategy.

The total inference time to obtain the results in Figure 39, Figure 41, and Figure 42 is generally lower than that of classical sparse recovery methods, although the latter show mixed behavior, with some approaches remaining computationally efficient while others incur noticeably higher inference costs. This apparent efficiency advantage of the machine learning models, however, is offset by a substantially higher training cost, whereas classical sparse recovery methods require no separate training phase and rely solely on inference-time computation.

Overall, the results reveal a consistent hierarchy across methods. Classical sparse recovery with operator-weighted scaling provides the most reliable and interpretable refinement patterns, consistently capturing sharp discontinuities and expansion features. Sketching without scaling leads to degraded performance due to loss of spectral structure, while scaling improves recoverability by restoring compressibility under dimensionality reduction. The graph-based machine learning models demonstrate encouraging generalization from a single training simulation but remain less robust in resolving fine-scale features under limited data. Collectively, these observations suggest that sparse mesh adaptation is governed more fundamentally by operator conditioning and spectral structure than by the choice of optimization or learning strategy. A detailed error analysis of these methods is presented in the next section.

20 Error Analysis Results

This subsection quantifies the accuracy of the proposed framework. Errors are evaluated using appropriate norms and compared across different configurations. The effect of sketching, scaling, and learning-based refinement on overall solution accuracy is analyzed.

20.1 Classical Methods

20.1.1 ℓ_0 Method: OMP

Iteration-wise Error Convergence

Figure 43: OMP: Iteration-wise AW-L1 error convergence. (AW = area-weighted)

The area-weighted L1 (AW-L1 error, as indicated in Figure 43) exhibits a significant decrease between the initial and first iteration, after which it stabilizes with small oscillations. Without operator-weighted scaling and under Rademacher sketching, the Jump operator typically requires up to two iterations to reach this stabilized regime.

All simulations reported in this study (including iteration-wise convergence results) are performed using a fixed number of five adaptation iterations. This choice is not special; it is a practical

setting sufficient for convergence in most cases, although some configurations may converge earlier or require additional iterations depending on flow complexity.

Figure 44: OMP: Iteration-wise AW-L2 error convergence. (AW = area-weighted)

The AW-L2 error shows a similar convergence pattern: rapid initial reduction followed by stabilization with small oscillations.

Operator and Sketching Comparison

Figure 45: OMP: AW-L1 error comparison of CellGrad, Jump, and VertexGrad operators with and without operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The AW-L1 error converges across all operator and sketching configurations. However, when operator-weighted scaling is not applied under sketching, a significantly higher number of cells is required to achieve comparable accuracy, indicating reduced efficiency despite convergence in error.

With operator-weighted scaling, sketching achieves a cell count comparable to the full system while reducing the dimensionality of the least-squares problem. As previously observed, the Jump operator may require up to two iterations to stabilize.

Figure 46: OMP: AW-L2 error comparison of CellGrad, Jump, and VertexGrad operators with and without operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The same trends are observed for AW-L2 error, with consistent convergence across configurations. Operator-weighted scaling is essential to maintain efficiency under sketching by preventing excessive increase in required cells.

CellGrad Operator: Scaling Comparison

Figure 47: OMP: AW-L1 error comparison for the CellGrad operator with operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The CellGrad operator converges in all cases. Under sketching without operator-weighted scaling, convergence requires significantly more cells, reducing efficiency. With scaling, sketching retains accuracy while maintaining a compact representation.

Figure 48: OMP: AW-L2 error comparison for the CellGrad operator with operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

Similar behavior is observed for AW-L2 error, confirming the stabilizing effect of operator-weighted scaling under sketching.

20.1.2 ℓ_1 Method: FISTA

Iteration-wise Error Convergence

Figure 49: FISTA: Iteration-wise AW-L1 error convergence. (AW = area-weighted)

The AW-L1 error decreases sharply in the first iteration and then stabilizes with small oscillations across all configurations.

All simulations follow a fixed five-iteration adaptation strategy, used consistently across all cases.

Figure 50: FISTA: Iteration-wise AW-L2 error convergence. (AW = area-weighted)

A similar convergence trend is observed for AW-L2 error.

Operator and Sketching Comparison

Figure 51: FISTA: AW-L1 error comparison of CellGrad, Jump, and VertexGrad operators with and without operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The AW-L1 error converges across all configurations. Without operator-weighted scaling under sketching, a higher number of cells is required for comparable accuracy, indicating reduced efficiency. With scaling, performance remains consistent with the full system.

Figure 52: FISTA: AW-L2 error comparison of CellGrad, Jump, and VertexGrad operators with and without operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The same trend holds for AW-L2 error, confirming robustness of operator-weighted scaling.

CellGrad Operator: Scaling Comparison

Figure 53: FISTA: AW-L1 error comparison for the CellGrad operator with operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

The CellGrad operator converges in all cases. Without scaling under sketching, convergence

requires significantly more cells, reducing efficiency.

Figure 54: FISTA: AW-L2 error comparison for the CellGrad operator with operator-weighted scaling across different sketching types. (AW = area-weighted)

Similar behavior is observed for AW-L2 error.

20.2 Combined Iteration-wise Error Comparison for Different Methods

Figure 55: Combined AW-L1 error analysis for $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 15^\circ$, using Jump operator with Rademacher sketching and operator-weighted scaling.

Figure 56: Combined AW-L2 error analysis for $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 15^\circ$, using Jump operator with Rademacher sketching and operator-weighted scaling.

All four methods (OMP, IHT, HTP, and FISTA) show rapid initial error reduction followed by stabilization. The number of cells used remains comparable across methods for the chosen configuration.

Figure 57: Density solutions for $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 15^\circ$ for the four methods under study.

20.3 Sketching Study: Influence of Sketching Dimension on OMP

In this study, we investigate how varying the sketching dimension affects the performance of the OMP (ℓ_0) method using Rademacher sketching. The number of rows in the sketching matrix

is varied via a *sketch factor*, which reduces the dimension of the original least-squares problem. Two scenarios are considered: without operator-weighted scaling (unweighted) and with operator-weighted scaling (weighted). The area-weighted L1 (AW-L1) and L2 (AW-L2) errors are reported to assess accuracy under compression.

20.3.1 OMP: Without Scaling

Figure 58: OMP: Area-weighted L1 error versus sketching dimension (unweighted). The error may not stabilize at higher sketch factors, indicating instability in the absence of operator-weighted scaling. (AW = area-weighted)

Figure 59: OMP: Area-weighted L1 error versus sketching dimension (operator-weighted scaling). The method maintains low error across sketch factors. (AW = area-weighted)

20.3.2 OMP: With Scaling

Figure 60: OMP: Area-weighted L2 error versus sketching dimension (unweighted). The error may not stabilize at higher sketch factors, indicating instability in the absence of operator-weighted scaling. (AW = area-weighted)

Figure 61: OMP: Area-weighted L2 error versus sketching dimension (operator-weighted scaling). The method maintains low error across sketch factors. (AW = area-weighted)

20.4 Perturbation Study: Effect of Right-Hand Side Scaling

To assess the robustness of the methods under perturbations in the right-hand side, we introduced scaled perturbations $\Delta B = \epsilon B$, where ϵ varies from 0.01 to 0.4. The study focuses on OMP (ℓ_0 method) and FISTA (ℓ_1 method) using the Jump operator, Rademacher sketching, and operator-weighted scaling.

20.4.1 ℓ_0 Method: OMP

As shown in Figures 62 and 63, OMP remains stable across the full range of perturbation scales. The area-weighted errors (AW-L1 and AW-L2, as indicated in the figures) exhibit negligible variation, indicating robustness of the reconstruction under right-hand side perturbations in this setting.

Figure 62: OMP: AW-L1 error convergence under varying right-hand side perturbation scales ϵ . (AW = area-weighted)

Figure 63: OMP: AW-L2 error convergence under varying right-hand side perturbation scales ϵ . (AW = area-weighted)

20.4.2 ℓ_1 Method: FISTA

As shown in Figures 64 and 65, FISTA shows similar robustness. The area-weighted errors (AW-L1 and AW-L2) remain stable across perturbation scales, confirming that the method is not sensitive to moderate variations in the right-hand side scaling.

Figure 64: FISTA: AW-L1 error convergence under varying right-hand side perturbation scales ϵ . (AW = area-weighted)

Figure 65: FISTA: AW-L2 error convergence under varying right-hand side perturbation scales ϵ . (AW = area-weighted)

20.5 Machine Learning Assisted Refinement

This subsection presents an initial assessment of machine learning-based refinement models, namely Graph Convolution Network (GCN) and Graph Attention Network (GAT). The evaluation is performed across three wedge angles, and the results are reported in terms of number of cells used and iteration-wise area-weighted L1 and L2 errors.

20.5.1 Baseline Physics-informed Classification Loss

Figure 66: Number of cells and iteration-wise area-weighted L1 and L2 errors for $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$.

For $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$, both GCN and GAT use a comparable number of cells. The area-weighted L1 and L2 errors decrease sharply from iteration 0 to iteration 1 and then stabilize with small oscillations across subsequent iterations.

Figure 67: Number of cells and iteration-wise area-weighted L1 and L2 errors for $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$.

A similar trend is observed for $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$. Both models yield comparable cell counts, and the errors exhibit a rapid initial decrease followed by stabilization.

Figure 68: Number of cells and iteration-wise area-weighted L1 and L2 errors for $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$.

For $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$, the same behavior persists. Both GCN and GAT produce comparable cell counts, and the error metrics decrease significantly in the first iteration before stabilizing.

Overall, across all cases, both GCN and GAT demonstrate consistent behavior in terms of convergence trends and cell usage, with no significant differences observed between the two architectures under the tested configurations.

20.5.2 Physics-informed Classification Loss with Multi-model High-precision Ensemble Approach

We also determine the training error with respect to the ensemble approach. Note that $error \neq loss$ here.

Figure 69: Training errors of GAT and GCN for $\theta_2 = 8^\circ$.

Figure 70: Training errors of GAT and GCN for $\theta_2 = -8^\circ$.

Figure 71: Training errors of GAT and GCN for $\theta_2 = 15^\circ$.

Figure 69, 70 and 71 show that both GCN and GAT training errors are lower than the original loss, shown in Figure 66, 67 and 68. This means the ensemble approach improved the original learning metric we proposed. The GCN and GAT results differ only slightly.

21 Discussion

From the results presented above, several consistent trends emerge:

- **Classical sparse recovery methods (OMP and FISTA):** Both ℓ_0 - and ℓ_1 -based formulations exhibit a sharp reduction in area-weighted L_1 and L_2 errors in the first iteration, followed by a stable regime with minor oscillations. When operator-weighted scaling is applied, the number of selected cells remains comparable across operators while maintaining accuracy under sketching.
- **Effect of operator-weighted scaling:** Scaling is essential for sketching-based sparse recovery. Without scaling, the methods require a significantly larger number of selected cells to achieve comparable accuracy, reflecting loss of effective conditioning under compression. With scaling, sketching preserves accuracy while operating on a reduced-dimensional system.
- **Influence of operators:** CellGrad and VertexGrad consistently converge faster, typically stabilizing within a single iteration under scaling. In contrast, the Jump operator may require up to two iterations to reach a stable solution depending on the configuration.
- **Method comparison:** Across OMP, IHT, HTP, and FISTA, convergence behavior is qualitatively similar, with rapid initial error reduction followed by stabilization. Despite differences in formulation, all methods achieve comparable sparsity levels in the scaled setting.
- **Machine learning-based refinement (GCN and GAT):** The graph-based models constitute a separate refinement workflow that directly learns refinement indicators from data rather than solving a sparse recovery problem. Across all θ_2 configurations, both GCN and GAT produce consistent refinement patterns with similar cell counts and rapid error reduction followed by stabilization. While they capture dominant structures reliably, fine-scale features are less sharply resolved compared to classical sparse recovery methods.

Overall, two distinct refinement paradigms are observed. Classical sparse recovery methods rely on an explicit operator-based formulation, where performance is strongly influenced by conditioning and spectral properties and is significantly improved by operator-weighted scaling under sketching. In contrast, the machine learning-based approach operates independently of the sensing operator structure, learning refinement patterns directly from data and therefore not governed by the same conditioning or scaling effects. These complementary perspectives highlight the distinct but parallel roles of classical sparse recovery and machine learning-based approaches in adaptive mesh refinement.

22 Conclusion

We consider the problem of mesh adaptation for numerical solutions governed by different discretization methods, with the objective of developing a robust and computationally efficient methodology that is independent of the underlying numerical scheme. The central goal is to reliably identify regions requiring refinement while maintaining applicability across different computational settings, ranging from classical adjoint-style optimization frameworks to data-driven learning approaches.

We first consider a sparse recovery-based method for discontinuity detection and mesh refinement. This approach is inherently interpretable, as refinement decisions arise directly from the structure of the sensing operator and the solution representation. It provides reliable identification of localized features through an explicit optimization framework, making it suitable in settings where transparency, robustness, and physical interpretability are important.

We then consider a machine learning-based approach using an ensemble of graph neural networks. This method addresses the same mesh refinement objective in a purely data-driven manner,

where a physics-informed classification loss is used to learn discontinuity indicators from discretized solution representations. This formulation is flexible and computationally efficient at inference time, particularly when repeated solution of expensive optimization or adjoint-like procedures is undesirable. However, this gain in efficiency comes at the cost of reduced interpretability, as the learned refinement strategy is not explicitly constrained by the underlying operator structure.

Overall, the two approaches provide complementary and independent strategies for mesh adaptation. Classical sparse recovery methods can be viewed as structured, optimization-driven refinements closely related to traditional adjoint-based workflows, offering strong interpretability and controllable behavior. In contrast, machine learning-based methods provide a fast, data-driven alternative that can generalize across configurations but lacks an explicit operator-based interpretation. Rather than competing approaches, they represent two ends of a spectrum, where the choice is governed by the trade-off between computational efficiency and interpretability.

This duality suggests that effective mesh adaptation is not tied to a single paradigm, but can instead be achieved through either principled optimization or learned approximation, depending on the demands of the application.

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